

Toolkit for measuring costs and benefits of managing peatland for ecosystem services

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Introduction

Peatlands are an iconic Scottish landscape which provide a range of ecosystem services, including provision of a historically and contemporarily important fuel source, connections to culture and heritage, unique biodiversity, and an important carbon store (Roberts, Mzek, *et al.*, 2023). Scotland's peat soils are estimated to store 3 billion tonnes of carbon (Scottish Government, 2022b), and are recognised by Scottish Government as being a key landscape to protect in the country's drive to net-zero. The importance of the peatland landscape means that Scotland's peatlands are widely managed for a range of different outcomes, and the Scottish Government has pledged over £250 million for peatland management between 2020 and 2030 (Forbes, 2020). Furthermore, upscaling of peatland management for carbon is an action within the Scottish Biodiversity Strategy, alongside actions to manage other uses of peatland landscapes, including sport shooting (Scottish Government, 2022a).

The large scale over which peatland management is being carried out, as well as the multitude of services peatlands may be managed for, means that cost-effective and equitable management of peatlands requires understanding of these services. Previous work has shown that current understanding of the value of peatland ecosystem services is dominated by carbon values, with a smaller amount of research into the value of other services (Roberts, Mzek, *et al.*, 2023). Given the finite funding available for peatland management estimating the value of the non-carbon benefits of peatland will enable management to be carried out which maximises across the range of benefits. This will improve cost-effectiveness of management where multiple services can be improved, and strengthen the justification for spending on peatlands. Equally, understanding any declines in value that may occur through changing management can enable management to be designed to limit these declines, or provide compensation if appropriate.

The benefits arising from peatland ecosystem services can be measured in a variety of ways. Economic valuation provides a way for benefits to be measured using a consistent comparator (i.e., monetary value), although care must be taken not to discount those benefits which are harder to value through monetary means (e.g., biodiversity). Methods of economic valuation can be broadly grouped into those that rely on market prices (market goods), and those that do not (non-market goods). Within the non-market goods methods may also be rooted in observed spending, known as revealed preferences, (e.g., travel cost) or hypothetical spending, known as stated preferences (e.g., contingent valuation).

Services considered

In previous work (results reported in: (Roberts, Mzek, *et al.*, 2023; Roberts *et al.*, 2024) we carried out a literature review and workshops, which identified 34 ecosystem services produced by Scottish peatlands, including services with extensive understanding of their value (e.g., carbon storage) and those for which values are less well understood (e.g., historical preservation). Through the stakeholder workshops we further identified high priority services for gathering valuation data. These were:

- water quality,
- flooding,
- energy,
- and timber (Roberts *et al.*, 2024).

It is these services that we will develop in this toolkit. For a list of the services considered see Appendix One, and for full results of the literature review and workshops see (Roberts, Mzek, *et al.*, 2023; Roberts *et al.*, 2024).

Objectives

This report has the objective of to create a toolkit which details methods to estimate the costs and benefits of managing peatland for ecosystem services for which high priority valuation gaps have been identified (Roberts *et al.*, 2024) through the specific research questions:

1. What are the benefits and disbenefits associated with the high priority services? Including identified relationships from Roberts *et al.*, 2024.
2. How can the value of the identified benefits be measured? Accounting for different resource availability where possible.
3. How can the costs of managing peatland for the identified ecosystem services be measured? Building on the costing framework developed in Roberts, 2024.

Methods and structure of toolkit

We will first present the benefits associated with each of the four high priority services for valuation (water quality, flooding, energy, timber). Benefits (and disbenefits) were identified first through conceptual maps presented in Roberts *et al.* 2024, which identified links between services provided by peatlands (Note: Not all of these services have consistent evidence within the scientific literature for their production in peatlands, however, we have included these services because they are identified by managers and policy makers as services that they would like to understand the value of in relation to peatlands). These services were then expanded to identify benefits arising from the services, as reported in the literature. From this long-list benefits were selected for inclusion in the toolkit where they:

- Were direct benefits from improvements to the service
- Were supported by one or more of the services identified.

For each of the benefits identified a further search of the literature was carried out to identify methods to measure their value. We present an overview of these methods, as well as making judgement on their resource needs and transferability of results. In addition, where possible we include examples of their application in peatlands.

The costs framework builds on that presented in Roberts, 2024, adapted to suit the development of new management for specific peatland services.

This toolkit cannot provide a step-by-step guide for carrying out the valuation, but points towards methods to be explored. The authors direct readers to the publications cited within this document, as well as the UK Government Green Book (HM Treasury, 2022) and Enabling Natural Capital Approach (ENCA, (Defra, 2023) for further details. Details of application of the toolkit to Scottish peatlands will be presented in later publications.

Toolkit

Methods for estimating (dis)benefits

Table 1 (Dis)benefits identified for each of the high valuation priority services for peatland management. For details of how (dis)benefits were identified see (Roberts et al., 2024).

Service	(Dis)benefit	(Dis)benefit context	Improve or decline	Method	Page
Water quality	Public health – inc. mental wellbeing	Improved public health and wellbeing through management to improve water quality. Improved public health and wellbeing also linked to increase in recreation, which may improve health and wellbeing.	Improve	Cost of illness	8
				Value of statistical life	17
				Value transfer	18
	Clean drinking water	Improved drinking water due to reduced pollution or chemicals.	Improve	Avoided damage costs	7
				Value of production	12
				Value transfer	18
	Water quality sensors lifespan	Increase lifespan of water sensors due to reduced turbidity of water.	Improve	Avoided damage costs	7
				Value transfer	18
	Jobs	Increased jobs in whisky, recreation and timber industries due to cleaner water.	Improve	Direct employment	9
				Input-output models	10
Local Multiplier 3 models				11	
Value transfer				18	
Flood and drought reduction	Clean drinking water	Improved water quality, leading to less cleaning requirements.	Improve	Avoided damage costs	7
				Value of production	12
				Value transfer	18
	Water quality sensors lifespan	Reduced equipment decline due to cleaner water.	Improve	Avoided damage costs	7
				Value transfer	18
	Jobs	Increased potential for food production, game, timber, whisky, and recreation	Improve	Direct employment	9
Input-output models				10	

Service	(Dis)benefit	(Dis)benefit context	Improve or decline	Method	Page	
				Local Multiplier 3 models	11	
				Value transfer	18	
	Regulated water availability	Water flow regulation leading to more consistent water availability. Linked to reduction in both flood and drought.	Improve	Avoided damage costs	7	
				Hedonic pricing	13	
				Travel costs	14	
				Contingent valuation	15	
				Choice experiment	16	
				Value transfer	18	
	Improved ambient water quality	Water flow regulation leading to improved water quality.	Improve	Avoided damage costs	7	
				Hedonic pricing	13	
				Travel costs	14	
				Contingent valuation	15	
				Choice experiment	16	
				Value transfer	18	
	Energy	Public health – inc. mental wellbeing	Public health decline due to reduced surface cooling and increased flood risk. Variable impacts on public health due to recreation, as access may be increased due to access road creation.	Decline (overall, some improvement in some areas possible)	Cost of illness	7
Value of statistical life					17	
Value transfer					18	
Jobs		Direct increases in jobs due to energy production.	Decline (overall, some improvement in some areas possible)	Direct employment	9	
				Input-output models	10	
		Potential changes or declines in jobs for cultural heritage, timber, food, recreation, game, tourism.		Local Multiplier 3 models	11	
				Value transfer	18	
Clean drinking water		Reduction in filtering toxic chemicals and water flow regulation likely increasing cleaning needed.	Decline	Avoided damage costs	7	
				Value of production	12	
				Value transfer	18	
				Decline	Avoided damage costs	7

Service	(Dis)benefit	(Dis)benefit context	Improve or decline	Method	Page
	Water quality sensors lifespan	Increased turbidity of water leading to more frequent water sensor decline.		Value transfer	18
	Regulated water availability	Water flow regulation disruption leading to less consistent water availability.	Decline	Avoided damage costs	7
				Hedonic pricing	13
				Travel costs	14
				Contingent valuation	15
				Choice experiment	16
				Value transfer	18
	Energy availability	Direct energy production	Improve	Value of production	12
				Value transfer	18
	Timber	Public health – inc. mental wellbeing	Declines in public health due to reduced flood prevention/mitigation	Decline	Cost of illness
Value of statistical life					17
Value transfer					18
Jobs		Direct jobs increase, with potential loss of job in food production and game hunting.	Improve (overall, some change may be seen in employment type)	Direct employment	9
				Input-output models	10
				Local Multiplier 3 models	11
				Value transfer	18
Clean drinking water		Reduction in filtering toxic chemicals and water flow regulation likely increasing cleaning needed.	Decline	Avoided damage costs	7
				Value of production	12
				Value transfer	18
Water quality sensors lifespan		Increased turbidity of water leading to more frequent water sensor decline.	Decline	Avoided damage costs	7
				Value transfer	18
Timber available		Direct timber production	Improve	Value of production	12
				Value transfer	18

Market based methods

Avoided damage costs

What does it measure?

Avoided damage costs methods assign value to environmental management through estimating the amount of money that would have been spent if the management had not taken place. For example, if a peatland is managed in such a way to reduce flood risk, then the money saved through not experiencing a flood event can be ascribed as a benefit of the management. In order to estimate future avoided damage costs modelling is used to predict how the environment will change (e.g., hydrological models of water flow rate and flood events). To measure avoided costs for management already in place measurements may be taken of costs before and after management was carried out, however, care must be taken to ensure that all changes are linked to management, and not other environmental or infrastructure changes (e.g., rainfall).

How could this be applied to peatland management?

Avoided costs in peatlands management are most likely related to flood mitigation and water quality improvements. Avoided damage costs are often reported at the state or company level, however, avoided damage costs to individuals can be estimated. For example, losses after previous flood events (Owusu, Wright and Arthur, 2015) may be used to estimate future avoided costs, particularly where personal property is threatened with flooding. Alternative management of peatland landscapes were compared in relation to their impacts on flood events in the Netherlands. Flood events were anticipated to reduce under land-use which increased water storage capacity in productive peatlands. In this example reed paludiculture showed highest value of avoided damages, while drainage based dairy systems demonstrated no value in flood reduction. (Liu *et al.*, 2023).

In water quality improvements achieved through peatland management avoided costs may arise from reduced maintenance and replacement of water sensors, and reduced cleaning of drinking water. Savings related to the longer life of water sensors may include savings associated with water testing, staffing, technicians, sampler, salaries, vehicle costs, hours sampling, distance travelled (Crocker and Bartram, 2014). For improved drinking water quality benefits of cost savings are estimated in terms of capital cost savings and operational cost savings of water pollution treatment associated with the effective catchment management (Glass and Burgess, 2023). Although estimating these costs is straightforward, care must be taken to account for any other changes in the catchment which may also impact water quality, including uncontrollable events such a change in rainfall. Avoided costs were estimated for avoided costs of water treatment for alternative scenarios for managing Keighley catchment, West Yorkshire. Avoided costs were calculated for the avoided operational costs of treating water, as well as the delay of needed capital investment in water treatment plant. In addition, this study also included the avoided carbon emissions due to reduced water treatment needs (Harlow *et al.*, 2012).

Resources needed

Data

The costs data required for calculating avoided damage costs will most often be secondary data routinely collected by institutions responsible for the costs (e.g., water cleaning). The

exception to this is likely to be costs to individuals, where surveys or interviews may be required (Owusu, Wright and Arthur, 2015).

Where predictive models are to be used to estimate future avoided damage costs data needs will be higher. The specifics of the data required will depend on the benefits being measured but are likely to include hydrological and weather data for the management site and catchment.

Analysis

Analysis needs for estimating avoided damage costs may vary significantly. Where damages avoided are direct (e.g., longer life of water quality sensors) analysis will be relatively straightforward comparison of costs before and after intervention, taking account of any other changes in the environment. Complexity in analysis will increase to estimate avoided damage costs for more indirect changes, which may be impacted by a wider variety of additional variables (e.g., flood mitigation). Where predictive models are used to estimate future avoided damages analysis needs may be significantly higher.

Transferability

Avoided damage cost estimates have the potential to be transferred between sites. Care must be taken to account for the scale of the likely damages in the new site (e.g., number of water sensors, frequency of flooding) and transferability will decline with increasing complexity of modelling of impacts.

Cost of illness

What does it measure?

Cost of illness approaches measure value through the avoided cost of treating illness that would occur without the intervention (Knapp and Wong, 2020). This method can be applied to specific illnesses or can be adapted to general health and wellbeing through additional models linking to healthcare costs. Illness may be directly caused by the environment (e.g., waterborne diseases), or have severity changed through exposure to the environment (e.g., mental health).

How could this be applied to peatland management?

With regards to peatland valuation direct cost of illness approaches are more readily applicable. For example cost of illness approaches have been used extensively with regards to drinking water and microbial risk (Bergion *et al.*, 2020). As with avoided damage costs, however, care must be taken that changes in frequency or severity of illness also take account of other environmental changes. Avoided costs of illness has been calculated for healthcare costs in relation to nitrogen pollutants in peatland habitats. Nitrogen addition was lowest in peatland management areas which included lower animal densities, and less intensive fertiliser application. These practises were therefore also associated with lower cost of illness (Liu *et al.*, 2023). In forest peatlands in South Sumatra interviews were held with communities to identify use and reliance on the peat swamp forest. Peat swamp forest degradation was predicted to have a future potential contribution of £225 (Rp. 4,558,887) increase in cost of illness per person per year as a result of peat degradation. The adverse health effects were anticipated due to increases in flood, drought, and fire events (Ulya *et al.*, 2018).

Although not yet, to our knowledge, used in peatland landscapes, there is a long history of using cost of illness approaches in relation to mental health and the management of urban parks and green spaces (Roberts, Colley, *et al.*, 2023). These studies typically use regression models between park visits or area and measures of mental health, which may be self-reported or secondary population level data. For example, surveys were used with park visitors reporting their health through standardised indices (Personal Wellbeing Index and K10). This health data was then regressed with frequency of visits, including additional variables which impact health. Multiplying the reduction in illness by national average costs of ill health enabled estimation of the avoided costs of illness due to park visits (Buckley *et al.*, 2019; Buckley and Chauvenet, 2022). This method could therefore be adapted for use in peatland landscapes used for tourism or recreation.

Resources needed

Data

Total cost of specific illnesses is generally available from secondary data, but there is no single database of costs and so sourcing the data will depend on the illness studied. Frequency or severity of illness can also be accessed from secondary data sources in some cases (e.g., SIMD for mental health disorders), however this data is only typically available at a population level. For individual health data primary data collection, through interview or survey, would be needed.

Analysis

Where illness is a direct result of management (e.g., waterborne illness) analysis is likely to be straightforward comparison, accounting for any additional changes which may impact illness rate. More complex modelling skills will be required where predictive models of future change is required, or where links between illness and peatland are less direct (e.g., mental health, cardiac health).

Transferability

Estimates of the cost of specific illnesses are most often estimated from national averages, and so are readily transferable between sites in the same country. Transferability of the estimated value of peatland management would further require peatland and users to be highly similar, and so transferability would be limited.

Direct employment

What does it measure?

The value of direct employment may be reported as the number of full-time equivalent jobs supported, and can also include income, skill levels, and knock-on economic impacts (some detailed below). When measuring the employment benefit of peatland management this should be compared to employment arising from alternative activities that would be carried out in the absence of peatland management. Where employment data is not available, surveys may be used to estimate the employment supported.

How could this be applied to peatland management?

Peatland management supports employment both in on the ground activities, and associated jobs such as admin or research. The value of management of peatlands for employment can be measured directly through employment records, identifying number of full-time equivalent job supported. Although not yet applied to the peatland management sector, this method of valuation has been used widely for the forestry sector (Edwards *et al.*, 2009; Rubio, Warhurst and Anderson, 2022). In addition, direct employment supported in other sectors (e.g., tourism) can also be identified (Edwards *et al.*, 2009).

We did not find any studies directly related to peatland management. However, surveys were used in EU countries (including the UK) to estimate employment in the horticultural industry in relation to peat. This included both those directly working with peat, and associated administrative roles. In 2005 the total jobs were estimated at 10,716 across the EU (Schmilewski, 2019).

Resources needed

Data

Although secondary data is widely used in forestry (Edwards *et al.*, 2009; Rubio, Warhurst and Anderson, 2022), it is likely that for peatland management primary data would need to be collected. For direct employment only a single phase of surveys would be needed, however, to include indirect employment a second, and potentially third, round of surveys would be required.

Analysis

Analysis of direct employment requires few resources, as employment can be reported directly. Additional analysis would be required for estimating the secondary or tertiary jobs supported to ensure that jobs attributed to peatland management are not double counted in other sectors, however analysis requirements remain low.

Transferability

Employment is likely to be transferable between sites, as long as type of management and area are taken into consideration. Scaling up of area under management will need careful consideration as not all jobs will increase with a 1-to-1 ratio of management size.

Input-output models

What does it measure?

Input-output models are financial models accounting for all inputs and outputs of a sector or business. The method is suited to capturing a snapshot of the outputs, including employment, of a given activity. Basic input-output models capture economic information only at a single point in time. However, extensions and modifications of this model include general equilibrium models and economic time series model, which incorporate historic economic trends to predict future economic scenarios as a comparator (Greenberg, Lahr and Mantell, 2007).

How could this be applied to peatland management?

While input-output models may be most obviously useful in peatland management in relation to provision of timber or energy, they can also be used to estimate impacts of natural disasters,

such as flooding, throughout many sectors of the economy (Greenberg, Lahr and Mantell, 2007).

In a Europe wide study of transition away from coal, peat and shale produced energy the benefits and losses of reducing peat energy production were estimated using an input-output model (RHOMOLO-IO). Across Europe peat energy production was predicted to support 6,313 direct jobs, and a further 5,909 indirect jobs (Mandras and Salotti, 2021). Input-output models have also been widely used in forestry, and so could be adapted for use in peatlands. This has included output and employment measured as a result of shifting from conifer to broadleaves (Eiser and Roberts, 2002), afforestation (Harrison-Mayfield, Dwyer and Brookes, 1998), or forestry management options (Edwards *et al.*, 2009).

Resources needed

Data

Input-output models have significant data needs, although sector-level data may be available as secondary data for peatland management in particular it is likely that primary data collection would be necessary. Primary data collection would likely be through survey or interview, and include: change in employment, use of contractors and advisors, changes in income, use of inputs, and sales of output. Analysis also relies on availability of multipliers from national level data, which may not be available for all industries at a scale that can be applied to peatland management.

Analysis

Skills needed for analysis is high, with large datasets across multiple economic sectors. This will increase for extended models, which also incorporate time series data.

Transferability

Input-output models have limited transferability of value estimates, however, the models themselves could be readily transferred between sites, with site specific variables entered. Input-output models are often carried out at large scales, and so values may be applicable over large areas without transfer.

Local multiplier 3 model

What does it measure?

Local multiplier models specifically consider how money spent locally impacts the local economy, typically following the first three rounds of spending. The models map the flow of money, including labour and materials, as it is spent within a defined area.

How could this be applied to peatland management?

This can be used to understand the local benefits of employment and spending (e.g., on materials) on peatland management. We are not aware of any use of local multiplier models in peatland management currently. However, the models have been used to estimate the impact of ecosystem services payment, identifying significant sub-regional income and employment effects of the injection of funds (Courtney *et al.*, 2013). This use of local multiplier 3 models may therefore be readily transferred to measure local impacts of funding for peatland management.

Resources needed

Data

Primary data collection is needed, with a potentially large number of businesses through three rounds of spending. Data collected includes financial information about the supplies procured for management, and the location of all procurement. Additional information about the spending that would occur in the absence of peatlands management would also need to be collected to ensure that models only incorporate additional spending.

Analysis

Resources needed for analysis are limited, as data collected are directly reporting spending.

Transferability

Transferability will be highly limited, as value will depend on where funding is spent, and availability of resources is likely to vary by location.

Value of production

What does it measure?

Value of production methods estimate the economic value of goods produced. They can also be used to measure increased labour productivity. Value of production can create a snapshot of the current value of peatland management, be monitored over time to demonstrate value of changing management, or be incorporated into production models to predict future changes. Where value of production is predicted into the future discount rates should be used to estimate net present value. The Green Book provides guidance on the most appropriate discount rates to apply (HM Treasury, 2022).

How could this be applied to peatland management?

Peatland can be managed directly for production, including for energy or timber. Additionally, management of peatland may have knock on impacts production of goods elsewhere, such as improved water quality leading to increased fish production. Finally, environmental exposure has been linked to workplace productivity (Buckley *et al.*, 2019; Buckley and Chauvenet, 2022), although peatland has not yet, to our knowledge, been explicitly studied for this impact.

Value of production methods can enable estimation of the production of energy provided through wind turbines sited on peatland sites. Here wind velocity is calculated as a function of wind speed, enabling calculation of power outputs. The value of the energy produced is calculated as a function of market price, exercise price, risk free return and time until realisation (Greenberg, Byalsky and Yahalom, 2021). The production of wind energy from proposed wind farm sites (in 2014) on blanket bogs in Scotland was estimated based on reported production of currently active sites. Although this estimate was not monetised, monetisation would be possible based on existing energy prices and running costs (Artz *et al.*, 2014).

Production of energy from peat is also achieved through extraction of peat for burning. In a Finnish case study the value of production of a new peat extraction site was estimated through discounted cash flow to estimate net present value. This included total volume of peat removed

from the site calculated across peat production period of 30-40 years as cumulative values, minus the costs of establishment, extraction, and haulage (Juutinen *et al.*, 2019). Although it is unlikely that extraction of peat for energy use in Scotland will increase, or that new sites will be established, value of production approaches can be applied to understand the decline in value of peat use for energy under alternative management scenarios.

The forestry sector uses value of production methods extensively in timber production, which can be applied directly to timber produced on peatland landscapes. Estimating the value of timber will include estimation of the volume of timber produced, and market value of the products (first grade wood, second grade wood, chipping wood) anticipated. Costs include felling and processing, transport to landing side, and extraction, including both labour and machinery costs (Accastello *et al.*, 2018). Data simulation models may also be used to estimate production on new or restocked sites (Başkent *et al.*, 2011).

Resources needed

Data

To create a snapshot estimate of value of production on peatlands data needs are relatively low and will predominantly be data which is collected by the institutions responsible for production as general monitoring. The exception to this would be for personal peat extraction, where data collection via survey or interview would be required, due to no central managing institution.

Where modelling to predict future production is needed, such as for wind farms or timber production, there will be higher data needs, which will require primary data collection on the characteristics of the site. Models will also require secondary industry-standard conversion to the final product (e.g., energy or timber)

Analysis

Similar to data requirements, analysis for a snapshot of value of production will be fairly straightforward and is likely carried out routinely by institutions responsible for production. More advanced modelling skills would be needed to estimate future production.

Transferability

Some transfer of production values may be possible, where sites are similar in characteristics. Care must be taken to account for any likely variation in productivity however, particularly with regards to scaling of production values.

Revealed preferences

Hedonic pricing

What does it measure?

Hedonic pricing is a method of estimating value of a non-market good (i.e., a good that is not brought or sold) based on the impact it has on a related market good. Most often this is done through house prices, however any good which may have prices influenced by the environment could be used. Value is estimated through regression analysis, whereby prices are related to access to the environment (most often through distance for house prices). Care must be taken to include all variables which may impact prices (e.g., number of rooms, size of garden, distance to amenities).

How can this be applied in peatland management?

The presence of peatland in a landscape may impact the housing market either through the impact it has on the landscape, or its contribution to other ecosystem services (e.g., water quality).

Hedonic pricing was used to estimate the value of rural landscapes in Germany using holiday rental prices. Although peatland was not included specifically, it was counted within the “wetland” category. Using regression analysis between the coverage of rural land covers in buffers around holiday properties, the presence of wetlands within a 20km buffer of holiday rentals increased price by 5.4% (Wüstemann, 2014).

The impact of previous flood events can be measured through hedonic pricing. In the immediate aftermath of flooding in England house prices were 24.9% lower in flooded postcodes than non-flooded postcodes (Beltrán, Maddison and Elliott, 2019). Applying hedonic pricing in this way to peatland management will require either previous hedonic pricing to have been carried out following a flood event at the site, or careful transfer of values from other flooded locations (see value transfer section below).

Resources needed

Data

Data required is most likely going to be secondary data in the form of house price sales, household characteristics, and other geographical information on environment and infrastructure. Although secondary data, a large sample size will be needed to enable variation in price and peatland management attributes to be observed.

Analysis

Some data analysis skills required to carry out regression analysis. Modelling skills may be needed to link peatland management to potential impacts (e.g., flood risk) depending on the element being modelled.

Transferability

Transferability is limited, due to the specific nature of housing markets and environmental variables. However, hedonic pricing is typically carried out over large geographical areas, due to the volume of data needed, and so average values may be transferred to similar areas.

Travel cost

What does it measure?

The travel cost method estimates the value of an environment based on the cost of travel to the location. Depending on the study this may also include the value of the time spent travelling to the location. Because it is based in true behaviour the travel cost method is considered more reflective of people’s true preferences, however, it can only be used to estimate the lower bound of the value, and not maximum willingness to pay.

How can it be applied to peatland management?

To compare management impacts using travel cost two approaches can be taken. Travel costs can be estimated before and after management change, with any change in travel cost attributed to the change in management. Alternatively, the travel cost to multiple sites with varied types of management may be estimated, and difference in costs between sites attributed to management differences. In both cases any differences in travel costs must also carefully take account of other differences between sites (e.g., changes to cost of living, weather, access roads).

Travel cost was used to estimate the recreation value of six Nordic landscapes, including one peatland (Simojoki, Finland). Surveys were carried out at common entry points to the landscape, collecting data on the number of visits to the location in the last 12 months, their travel cost, perceptions of water quality and conservation, and sociodemographic variables. Simojoki had lower recreational demand compared to other landscapes, but the second highest value per visit, of €63.70/visit (Juutinen *et al.*, 2019).

Resources needed

Data

Primary data collection is typically required. This may be through on-site surveys, or surveys sent to a mailing list of site visitors. Because large sample sizes are needed data collection can be extensive. Additional data will be needed on other environmental, infrastructure, and individual variables which may impact travel.

Analysis

Some data analysis is required, typically using regression analysis. Careful consideration needs to be taken for additional variables and distribution of travel costs.

Transferability

Some transferability possible to locations with similar environments and accessibility. Care needs to be taken that both access and environment are similar.

Stated Preferences

Contingent valuation

What does it measure?

The contingent valuation approach estimates peoples stated value of a non-market good (i.e., a good that is not brought or sold). Contingent valuation involves asking individuals the amount they would be willing to pay (WTP) for improvements in goods, or the amount the willingness to accept (WTA) as compensation for loss of goods that are not traded in the market (OECD, 2018). Because contingent valuation requires statement of hypothetical payment, surveys feature a detailed description of the hypothetical market which must be clear and meaningful to the respondents, who must clearly comprehend the proposed changes in characteristics of the goods or service they are asked to value.

In addition to contingent valuation this method can also be adapted to contingent behaviour. In contingent behaviour rather than scenarios varying in price, respondents may indicate how their behaviour will change in response to changes in environmental scenarios.

How can this be applied to peatland management?

Contingent valuation has been used widely to measure environmental values which cannot be estimated from markets. Because contingent valuation relies on hypothetical scenarios can be particularly useful to value future changes in management.

Contingent valuation can be applied to flood mitigation to estimate non-market impacts, such as the psychological aftermath of experiencing a flood event. UK households were willing to pay £653 per year to avoid intangible impacts of flooding, with stress and worry about future flood events key indicators of higher willingness to pay (Joseph, Proverbs and Lamond, 2015).

Preferences for environmental states can also be measured through contingent valuation. The value of reductions in eutrophication in Denmark was estimated through a survey of residents, with an average willingness to pay of €12/month (Atkins and Burdon, 2006).

Contingent behaviour is often applied to measures of recreational value, and can be linked to travel cost methods (see page 14). For example to measure the impact of water quality visitors to coastal areas were asked how their future planned visits would change if water quality increased or decreased (Hanley, Bell and Alvarez-Farizo, 2003).

Resources needed

Data

Contingent valuation studies require primary data collection with large sample sizes. Surveys can be implemented at individual or household level, and can be conducted by mail, phone or in person. In-person interviews are more likely to be completed fully and provide better data quality as additional background information can be provided on the spot. However, depending on the size of the sample targeted and the budget available, this is often unfeasible.

Analysis

Contingent valuation requires moderate data analysis skills, to model the relationship between stated preferences and environmental change.

Transferability

In general, contingent valuation estimates are limited in their transferability. To transfer a value estimate, both the scenarios involving the service or the product to be valued and the specifics target population surveyed (e.g., importance of the service or product in question to the certain demographics or community) must be similar. Additionally, aspects such as currency, purchasing power, and disposable income in primary and secondary study locations have to be considered and adjusted.

Choice Experiment

What does it measure?

The choice experiment approach involves asking people to make a choice between multiple hypothetical scenarios, each described by several attributes as well as an associated cost. Choice experiments measure stated willingness to pay (or willingness to accept, in the case of disbenefits) for each of the environmental attributes based on the trade-offs made between the

hypothetical scenarios. As with all stated preference methods, because this is a hypothetical scenario care must be taken to construct a scenario that is readily understood by respondents and is realistic within the environment.

How can this be applied in peatland management?

Choice experiments have been used extensively in peatlands, including in Scotland. They have been used to explore location of peatland management for carbon, biodiversity, and water, geographical location of management, and timing of management in particular. We present two examples of choice experiments used in Scottish peatlands.

A choice experiment was carried out comparing preferences for the share of peatlands improved, whether the improvements are carried out in wild land (remote) areas, and whether the area restored has a high or low concentration of peatland. Overall a positive willingness to pay for peatland restoration was found, with a higher willingness to pay for those individuals with a higher attachment to Scotland, and a more positive attitude to peatlands (Faccioli *et al.*, 2020).

To understand preferences for timing of peatland restoration for carbon, water quality, and wildlife a choice experiment was carried out with Scottish residents. Options were described in terms of share of peatland in good quality by 2050, and timing of restoration between 2017 and 2050. Overall benefits to Scottish households was estimated to be £77.76/household for early restoration, and £149.80/household/year for 40% of peatland to be in good quality by 2050 (Glenk *et al.*, 2021).

Resources needed

Data

Choice experiments require large sample sizes, and can potentially be long or complex surveys to complete. As a result, collection of data can often be time consuming. In many cases choice experiments use online survey panels to reduce the resources needed for data collection, however these can be expensive.

Analysis

Analysis of choice experiments requires choice modelling skills, as well as careful consideration of other impacts of economic choices.

Transferability

As with contingent valuation, choice experiment estimates are limited in their transferability. To transfer a value estimate, both the scenarios involving the service or the product to be valued and the specific target population surveyed.

Value of statistical life

What does it measure?

The value of statistical life estimates a value for additional life-years given as a result of an intervention, adjusted for quality of life. The value of statistical life is estimated from stated willingness to pay to maintain life and includes Quality Adjusted Life Years (QALY) and Disability Adjusted Life Years (DALY) (Knapp and Wong, 2020). This approach to valuing health benefits

typically uses stated preference methods to estimate value placed on extending life or improving health related quality of life. This can include choice experiments or contingent valuation (as described elsewhere in this toolkit), as well as other survey questions including:

- Standard Gamble – where the certainty of a certain life span are traded off with a gamble or perfect health or death
- Time trade off – where length and quality of life are traded off.

Quality Adjusted Life Years are a standard measure of benefit within healthcare, estimated from life expectancy and quality of life measures. The value of QALY is relatively consistent across developed countries, estimated in the Green Book as £70,000/year (HM Treasury, 2022). This measure is typically applied to long-term changes to quality of life, such as disablement or long-term health conditions, with the value estimated over a lifetime. This value can be discounted over time, but this is controversial (Whitehead and Ali, 2010).

Similar to QALY, Disability Adjusted Life Years measure the relative impact of illness or injury on healthy life years. DALY are weighted by the amount a condition is thought to impact health condition, and standard values are available (Whitehead and Ali, 2010).

How can this be applied to peatland management?

Measurement of QALY change due to management can be through on-site surveys, comparing a standard measure of health to the national average for visitors, or may be through national level surveys, where regression of health can be made to use of outdoor spaces (Buckley *et al.*, 2019). We did not find any studies using QALY to measure the value of peatland management.

Resources needed

Data

Primary data collection is preferred (Buckley *et al.*, 2019), and would likely be required for assessment of statistical value of life in peatlands due to lack of existing data. This would also require large sample sizes.

Analysis

Final analysis is typically through a single step linear regression, so limited modelling is required. However, careful consideration of additional variables is needed.

Transferability

The average value of QALY is stable across developed countries (Buckley *et al.*, 2019), and so can be readily transferred (although it is important to note that this is an average, and so cannot be applied to an individual). For transfer of relationships between QALY and peatland management transfer would only be possible where management and relationship is similar. Similar transferability would be expected for DALY, requiring transfer only to similar management (Whitehead and Ali, 2010).

Value transfer (including meta-analysis)

What does it measure?

Value transfer refers to taking quantitative value estimates from existing primary valuation studies, adjusting these and applying them to another site that of interest to policy or research.

This approach is particularly favourable where time or resource constraints prevents collection of primary data at required scale. There are two main types of value transfers: unit value transfer and value function transfer (Grammatikopoulou *et al.*, 2023).

Unit value transfer takes values from a single primary study, with data often drawn from one study site. This approach requires a high level of similarity between the sites where the primary valuation study is conducted and where the value is going to be transferred.

Value function approaches (e.g., meta-analysis) have greater capacity to adjust for contextual differences than single unit transfers (Grammatikopoulou *et al.*, 2023) and reduce the degree to which similarity required between primary and transfer sites. In terms of accuracy and validity, function transfers have advantage over the unit transfers because they combine information from multiple primary studies to produce broad value functions.

How can it be applied to peatland management?

Because value transfer uses valuation from other primary valuation studies it can be used to value a wide range of services impacted by peatland management.

A meta-analysis was carried out for the economic value of wetlands, including peatlands. No specific peatland values are estimated, however the analysis identified water flow rate regulation and water quality improvements as the most highly valued services for wetlands overall. Value also increased for wetlands under higher human pressure, linked to higher use values (Ghermandi *et al.*, 2008).

Wetland values, including peatland values, were also analysed for flood control, water supply and nutrient cycling for agriculture. For wetlands as a whole values ranged from \$3389/ha/yr for water supply, to \$6923/ha/yr for flood control. These values varied by wetland type, however no peatland specific values are reported (Brander, Brouwer and Wagtendonk, 2013).

Resources needed

Data

By definition value transfer studies use secondary data, typically from published research. Volume of data required will vary, with higher resources are needed for a meta-analysis, which must include a full systematic literature review.

Analysis

Value transfer studies require careful analysis and application of values to new locations. They require adjustments in aspects such as currency and purchasing power, between the primary valuation study site and the transfer site. The more similar transfer and primary study areas are in terms of benefits, size, policy context and populations, the more valid value transfers will be (Grammatikopoulou *et al.*, 2023).

Transferability

Value transfer estimates have, by definition, already been transferred. As such, estimates themselves would be unsuitable to transfer to a new location. However, the underlying

valuation, and the value function, applied in value transfer studies are highly transferable, as long as new contexts are accounted for.

Costs

Previous work has developed a framework for costing biodiversity relation actions within Scotland (Figure 1 (Roberts, 2024)). This framework was developed with stakeholders from across Scottish environmental management and policy, and tested on actions in the Scottish Biodiversity Strategy Delivery Plan (Scottish Government, 2022a), including peatland management for carbon and biodiversity. Because this toolkit is intended to incorporate additional services, we detail the further considerations that will need to be included to apply the costing framework.

Figure 1 Framework for costing actions for biodiversity in Scotland. Reproduced from Roberts, 2024.

1. Where actions are extensions of existing work current costs can be easily incorporated into new estimates. However, when additional or new management goals are incorporated existing cost data may not be available for all planned actions. If the current actions do not meet the desired outcomes, costs may need to be incorporated from elsewhere. This may be from different environments (e.g., non-peaty wetlands) or from other locations. Incorporating costs data from other locations or environments will increase the uncertainty of costs, this can be reduced through sourcing data from as similar countries (e.g., matching climate and peat type) or environments (e.g., wetlands rather than forest) as far as possible, and sourcing costs from a high number of projects. Reporting minimum, average, and maximum costs, broken down into cost per unit (e.g., per ha) will make uncertainty visible.
2. Costs and savings arising from new technology may be particularly relevant for new peatland management actions to be introduced. Where new machinery would need to be purchased or hired identifying new methods to ensure capital spending is targeted to the most up-to-date method.

3. Existing capacity and skills within teams and institutions that underpin the new actions, although may not directly contribute. The addition of new management actions and management goals may mean that these underlying teams also require new training, or need to be expanded or link to other teams with expertise in other areas (e.g., forestry). This liaising with other teams will also incur a transaction cost, which should be included here.
4. Estimating the scale of increase needed for the inclusion of new management may also require additional consideration for the new management to be included. Higher numbers of additional staff may be needed if new activities are to be carried out alongside previous activities, or training costs may be high where existing staff need to carry out new management. In the first year capital costs of resources may also increase due to new equipment needed.
5. As with existing actions, the scale of increase in costs may not be linear with the scale of increase in action:
 - a. The law of diminishing returns states that for each additional £ spent, the return is lower.
 - b. Economies of scale refers to the fact that it is often cheaper per unit (e.g., ha) to carry out an action over a larger area than a smaller area.
6. For longer term actions the time period over which the project will take place should be determined, including the period over which maintenance will be required (which may be in perpetuity). Inflation should then be added each year, based on an average of the Consumer Price Index from the Bank of England.
7. From this new cost estimate a per unit cost should be estimated. Where new actions are being added to existing action cost estimates a breakdown in terms of “new” vs “old” actions may also be helpful, to feed into subsequent cost benefit analysis.
8. The addition of new management objectives may mean that alignment with new or different policies, plans, or actions should be considered (e.g., forestry). These should be identified and any synergies identified to improve cost effectiveness of the actions. Additionally, any contradictions between existing policies, plans, or actions should be recognised, so that these can be reduced or accounted for.
9. Finally, this framework presents only costs of actions. Decisions must also take account of the effectiveness of the action, any additional benefits, including for wider policy aims, and current capabilities, training, and resource availability. The costs estimated through this framework can therefore be combined with benefits as measured

Next steps

We have presented here options for measuring the value of peatland ecosystem services that were identified as of high importance through literature review and stakeholder consultation. While we do not present a step by step “how to” guide, we signpost methods to be considered, with some idea of the resources needed, and the transferability of the results. This research will be taken forward to measure these peatland management benefits at case study sites in Scotland, as part of the Scottish Government RESAS Strategic Research Program project CentrePeat (JHI-D3-2), and linked to ENCA (Defra, 2023) and Scotland’s Natural Capital Accounts. Results of this will be available by March 2027.

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Appendix One: Peatland ecosystem services

The full range of ecosystem services identified as produced by Scottish peatlands. For full report see Roberts et al. 2024.

- Carbon Storage
- Timber
- Financial Returns (Carbon credits)
- Flooding prevention
- Water Quality
- Jobs in Rural Areas
- Surface Cooling (Albedo)
- Energy
- Recreation
- Growing Media
- Food
- Game
- Wildlife Watching
- Recreational Environment of Biodiversity
- Scientific Interest
- Wellbeing
- Agriculture/ Grazing
- Whisky Industry
- Air Quality
- Archaeology/Paleoenvironments research
- Building
- Biodiversity Credits
- Disease Control
- Educational Services
- Historical Preservation
- Cultural Heritage
- Regulation of Water Scarcity
- Mitigation of Fire Risk
- Fish Farming
- Military Training Grounds
- Commercial Use for Recreation
- Filter Toxic Chemicals
- Wildfire Mitigation